

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART XX

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Hitherto-unknown 4:5-4':5'-diphenyl-bis-(3"-hydroxy-1"-thiophene)-thioether has been prepared and condensed with *o*-diketones, and thus indigoid dyes have been prepared with the object of studying colour and chemical constitution of these dyes.

In the present communication dithioindigoid dyes have been prepared, starting from diphenyl thioether. The diphenyl thioether has been sulphonated (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 994) and the resulting 4:4'-disulphonic acid through acid chloride, mercaptan and dithioglycolic acid, and subsequent cyclisation has been converted into 4:5-4':5'-diphenyl-bis-(3"-hydroxy-1"-thiophene)-thioether, all unknown. This thioindoxyl has been subsequently condensed with *o*-diketones to furnish dithioindigoid dyes. The dithioindoxyl obtained in this case was very impure and could not be purified due to its susceptibility to oxidation. The yield, as compared with others reported previously, is extremely poor. It produces a violet precipitate of the bis-indigo when oxidised by potassium ferricyanide in alkaline solution. The dyes, excepting the isatin compound, are almost insoluble in alkaline hydrosulphite and as such a very light shade has been obtained. On a comparison of these dyes with similar dithioindigoid dyes, described in Part XVI and XVII (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 497'; 1956, 33, 54), apparently no appreciable change in colour has been noticed, but a study of the absorption spectra in xylene solution reveals that the ether linkage -O- has the greatest bathochromic effect on the colour of these dyes (Table I).

TABLE I

	Absorption maxima.	
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenoether-2:2-bis-acenaphthylene-indigo	...	525 m μ
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenoethioether-2:2-bis-acenaphthylene-indigo	...	530
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenomethane-3:3-bis-indol-indigo	...	540
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenoether-3:3-bis-indol-indigo	...	540
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenoethioether-3:3-bis-indol-indigo	...	510
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenomethane-1:1-bis-acenanthrene-indigo	...	515
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenoether-1:1-bis-acenanthrene-indigo	...	520
4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiophenoethioether-1:1- do	...	520

The structures of the compounds described in this paper may be represented by the following formulae :

EXPERIMENTAL

Diphenyl thioether-4:4'-disulphochloride was prepared by heating a mixture of diphenyl thioether potassium disulphonate (18 g.), PCl_5 (15 g.) and POCl_3 (5 c.c.) on a water-bath for 2 hours and distilling off the POCl_3 under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was then treated with crushed ice, filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from toluene, m.p. 157° , yield, 10.5 g. (Found: C, 37.45; H, 2.15. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 37.6; H, 2.09 per cent).

Diphenyl thioether-4:4'-dimercaptan was prepared by heating the above disulphochloride (10 g.) with tin and HCl (conc.) for 6 hours when crystals of the mercaptan began to deposit in the inner tube of the condenser. After cooling, the solid was filtered, washed and extracted with benzene; the benzene extract was dried with CaCl_2 , filtered and benzene distilled off. The residue was then crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 118° , yield 5 g. (Found: C, 57.51; H, 4.18. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{S}_2$ requires C, 57.6; H, 4.0 per cent).

Diphenyl thioether-4:4'-dithioglycollic acid was prepared by dissolving the mercaptan (20 g.) in 10% NaOH and warming the filtrate with monochloroacetic acid (16 g.), previously neutralised with caustic soda for an hour. The filtered solution on acidifying with HCl produced the thioglycollic acid as a white precipitate, which on crystallisation from alcohol furnished white needles, m.p. $188\text{--}89^\circ$, yield 25 g. (Found: C, 52.51; H, 4.05. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$ requires C, 52.46; H, 3.82 per cent).

4:5-4':5'-bis-(3'-hydroxy-1''-thiophene)-thioether (I).—It was prepared by cyclising the dithioglycollic acid through its acid chloride (m.p. 77°) by anhydrous AlCl_3 in petroleum ether solution (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$), as described in previous communications (*loc. cit.*). This thioindoxyl, yield of which was extremely poor, could not be obtained in a pure condition. The bis-indigo was produced as a violet precipitate from its alkaline solution with potassium ferricyanide.

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-thioether-3:3-bis-indol-indigo (IIa) was prepared by mixing the separate acetic acid solutions of the dithioindoxyl and isatin and heating the mixture with HCl (conc., 1 c.c.) for half an hour when colour of the solution changed to deep red, and a violet precipitate separated out. This was filtered, washed with acetic acid and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a reddish violet crystalline mass, m.p. above 300° . It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with a chocolate colour and dyes cotton from yellow hydrosulphite vat in pinkish violet shade. Its absorption maxima is $510\text{ m}\mu$. (Found: C, 65.13; H, 2.93. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 65.30; H, 2.72 per cent).

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-thioether-2:2-bis-acenaphthylene-indigo (IIb) was prepared just like the previous compound from thioindoxyl and acenaphthenequi-

none as a violet-red precipitate and crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 295° . In H_2SO_4 (conc.) it dissolves with a greenish colour. It is very slightly soluble in alkaline hydrosulphite and dyes cotton in pinkish violet shade. Its absorption maxima is $520 m\mu$. (Found: C, 72.61; H, 2.92. $C_{40}H_{18}O_4S_2$ requires C, 72.94; H, 2.73 per cent).

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-thioether-9:9-bis-phenanthrene-indigo (IIc) was prepared from thioindoxyl and phenanthrenequinone as a chocolate precipitate. As the quantity was very small it could not be properly purified and studied.

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-thioether-1:1-bis-aceanthrene-indigo (IIId) was prepared from the thioindoxyl and aceanthraquinone as a deep chocolate precipitate and crystallised from xylene as a brownish violet mass, m.p. 278° with previous shrinking at 180° . It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with a green colour and is almost insoluble in hydrosulphite vat, dyeing cotton in light pinkish shade. Its absorption maxima is $520 m\mu$. (Found: C, 75.63; H, 3.1. $C_{48}H_{22}O_4S_2$ requires C, 75.98; H, 2.9 per cent).

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